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CUSTOMER PERCEPTION OF INSURANCE AND ITS INFLUENCE ON LIFE SATISFACTION: EMPIRICAL STUDY THROUGH CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In today's competitive world, life satisfaction that too more specifically customer satisfaction is the most important aspect to every company which retain customer to grow and to survive as satisfied customer is the greatest brand ambassador to attract the prospective customers to the company. The above saying is true, especially in the service sector like insurance. The aim of this study is to measure relationships between two different types of insurance i.e. life and motor insurance. The study aims to prove that though life insurance is different from motor insurance but both them as a matter of indemnity tries to engender life satisfaction. This proposition was studied though a sample survey and the data so collected was analyzed though correlation analysis coupled with structural equation modeling. Though the study could not find relationships as significant but finally able to prove the study hypothesis through Structural Equation Modeling.

Keywords: life insurance, motor insurance, life satisfaction, confirmatory factor analysis, structural equation modeling.

INTRODUCTION

Individual satisfaction is the most important element of societal wellbeing. The goal of business is to serve and provide goods and services to satisfy the needs of customers in return for a profit (Chiu CM *et al* 2012). However, to achieve, enhance and maximize customer satisfaction requires a lot of tangible and intangible resources (Wong, R. *et al* 2014). Customer satisfaction is the perception of customers on the service whether that service has met his needs and expectations. The quality of service, personal demographic and psychological factors, perception of equity and fairness, price, product quality, situational

factors, and attributions for service success or failure are the factors that influence the customer satisfaction. Security has been a universal desire right from the earliest civilizations. This quest for security has led to the concept of insurance. Insurance is a contract between two parties whereby one party called insurer undertakes, in exchange for a fixed sum called premium to pay the other party an assured sum of money on the occurrence of a certain event. Life insurance protects against the economic loss in the event of death. A family is generally dependent for its food, clothing, and shelter on the income brought by the bread earner of the family. So long as he lives, that family secure but the death of the person may put the family in a very difficult situation. The consumer decision making process for buying a life insurance product is hold true as in case of any ordinary product.

This is not the era of monopoly where only one exist and rule over the market, rather, this is the phase of globalization, liberalization, and privatization where the doors are opened for all to enter in to the domestic market and operate freely with certain regulations, which gives rise to immense competition in the market and creates anomalies in market, so in order to survive in this phase any firm has to focus on driving desired amount of satisfaction from their customers. In this era not the private sector but the public sector – big fish (LIC) as well has a lot of problem in maintaining customer satisfaction as due to intense completion and huge amount of alternative present in the market the customers' expectations are rising, to meet up these expectation the insurers has do develop a 'X' factor in their products and services, because a customer is said to be satisfied when he/she gets more than their expectations (Pathak, Bharthi V. 2010).

Insurance penetration in India is very low therefore there is a need to develop more insurance education among the masses that will help the insurance industry to grow. In my study the attitudes of the customers are very positive regarding in insurance most of the respondents from the sample would like to invest in insurance because of various reasons and unique features of insurance which is not there in any other investment options, and most striking feature is that the most of the people do not a fixed or heavy lump sum amount to be deposited in the traditional investment option like fixed deposit, therefore insurance provided them the ease of depositing money in part that is in premium to insurance policy on their convene any time in the time i.e. half yearly, monthly , yearly, or quarterly as well as it also benefits for tax savings which is also not the features of ant traditional investment options. So there is a much wider scope of insurance in India with regard to customer attitudes.

Mahajan, K (2013) did a study and analysis on customer decision making process on life insurance services and the study finds that by understanding financial services customer can improve business for companies on the basis of better service received. The insurance firms strive to identify customer requirements and develop strategies that allow them to meet or beat the service level provided by their competitors. Mushtaq, G. (n.d.) did a study on consumer attitude and its effect on BLC of life insurance companies. This study was conducted in the city of Lucknow by conducting a survey on 150 sample respondents. The purpose of the study is to find and assess the after sales service in life insurance companies. The study finally concludes that “that insurance is the booming industry that needs to care a lot of the customer as being a player in the service industry the insurance companies would like to draw more attention and focus on the customer attitudes and change in their preferences for the services to rendered.”

OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was done in April, 2015 in Hyderabad. A sample size of 310 individuals were interviewed with a structured and undisguised questionnaire having 30 questions. This study is the part of the whole effort. So, the description is provided for only 6 variables of the study. Each of three variables that deal with life insurance and motor insurance and they were analyzed by using SEM by using multivariate regression analysis in Calc. The following are the questions used for the study.

1. Insurance provide indemnity and it is a good investment option.
2. Investing in insurance provides increased happiness and life satisfaction.
3. Investing in insurance is a matter of personal responsibility also helps you fulfill family and social responsibility.

The above questions are general these questions were framed for both life and motor insurance so there will be 6 questions in the study. Structural equation modeling was done on the data sets through Onyx. Few tests like multivariate normality, multicollinearity were done in Libre Office Calc. The SEM performed in order to identify if any latent variables exists in the data set. The study proposes two latent variables on for life insurance and the other for motor insurance. A model with such intension is defined and measures were interpreted

accordingly after inspecting the output files. The purpose of the study is to find out if life insurance together with motor insurance could engender life satisfaction. The null hypothesis (H_0) is that *life insurance is not different from motor insurance in influencing life satisfaction. In other words, the difference is insignificant.* The following are the objectives to the study.

1. To know and assess respondents perception about life insurance.
2. To know and assess respondents perception about motor insurance.
3. To know if there exist any relationships between life insurance and motor insurance.
4. To understand and internalize if life insurance and motor insurance could influence life satisfaction at equal level.

The first three objectives can be studied through correlation analysis whereas the last objective strictly needs confirmatory factor analysis due to the fact that this objective verily related to the study hypothesis. The following part of this study provide description as what is SEM and its methodology.

About SEM: Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is an extension to generalized linear modling (GLM). The concept of SEM has roots to its parent concept systems of linear equations. SEM generally used to inspect complex relationships through confirmatory factor analysis. The methodology requires to inquire these relationships through path diagrams where the dependencies are explored through certain elements of the diagram namely arrows, cubes, squares and circles. As far as procedure is concerned the reasearcher specified the model through a simple covariance matrix and after performing SEM the resultant outputs will be interpreted through fit indices and other measures. In general the input for SEM is always a covariance matrix and which is subjected to analysis by specifying a model. After the analysis the model based covariance matrix will be obtained and interpreted accordingly. As far as nomenclature is concerned, SEM has certain jargon native to the methodology. Most importantly there are two phrases often used while performing analysis, they are manifest or observed variables and facets or latent variables. The unobserved variables are always represented by circles or ovals whereas observe or manifest variables are represented by rectangles or squares. Covariances are represented by bidirectional arrows where as relationships are represented by unidimensional arrows. At times variances are indicated by 1 in order to get standardized models and it is often regarded as a necessity for modelling.

Why SEM? SEM has many advantages in social research methods. The following are the advantages of using sem.

1. The assumptions underlying statistical analyses are clear and testable.
2. The advantage of using GUI.
3. The measures like regression coefficients, means, variances are compared simultaneously.
4. The advantage of using confirmatory analysis in stead of exploratory analysis.
5. Ability to fit non-standard and non-normally distributed data.
6. Provides unifying framework for linear models using flexible rather robust software.

SEM got to meet certain assumptions top of the above mentioned points. The foremost assumption is that the research needs a reasonable sample size. There is lot of literature to deal with this part of SEM, one thumb rule for managing problems that might arise due to sample size is to have at least 15 cases for each variable. There is also literature that affirm different figures depending on number of variables. Few studies advise to have at least 30 and other studies advise more than 100 cases. So it depends on the researcher to decide about the sample size and it is very much relative to number of parameters which directly depends on number of variables. The other assumption is that this analysis require to satisfy the principle of normality. SEM assumes that the input data is approximately normally distributed. In case of violation or or if the data is non-normal then analysis might need rather more samples. One more assumption is that the endogenous variables (also known as meadiators) must be normally distributed and the residuals not only satisfy univariate normality but the joint distribution should satisfy multivariate normality. However, there are number of ways to deal with non-normal data. Several models are developed to perform SEM on non-normal data. Savalei, V (2001)., Yuan, K-H. et al (2005) Bentler, P M., Yuan, K-H. (1999) and etc. are so classical resources that through lot of information on SEM on non-normal data.

There are three models that can be identified through SEM analysis. They are known as (1) just identified: a model in which there is exactly one solution for model parameters, (2) under-identified: a model in which there are infinite number of solutions for model parameters, (3) over-identified: a model in which there are as many known parameters as many unknown. Usually researchers interest is to probe for the third scenario, where this approach makes it feasible for posing restriction on the model through positive degrees of

freedom together with chi-square measure. When research reach to this level the researcher is actually trying to test the hypothesis that the model identified is actually do not deserve to be referred as a model of fitness.

ANALYSIS

The analysis is divided into two parts; the first deal with correlation analysis and the later deal with the structural equation modeling. The correlation matrix is computed in Libre Office Calc through data analysis menu. The correlation coefficients computed through Calc are Karl Pearson Product-moment correlation coefficients. The following table shows the details of correlations among study variables.

Part 1: Correlation analysis

Correlations	LI1	LI2	LI3	MI1	MI2	MI3
LI1	1					
LI2	0.068218828	1				
LI3	0.1872345944	-0.326607169	1			
MI1	-0.095263207	0.0649617791	-0.015290577	1		
MI2	-0.143270467	0.065181195	0.1303828897	0.1889995556	1	
MI3	-0.104811613	0.0988286595	0.0557267829	0.1833332806	-0.025089189	1
T measures	LI1	LI2	LI3	MI1	MI2	MI3
LI1	NA					
LI2	0.3618230167	NA				
LI3	1.0085890141	-1.828518314	NA			
MI1	-0.506388504	0.3444730365	-0.080919589	NA		
MI2	-0.766018629	0.3456414898	0.6958614732	1.018446937	NA	
MI3	-0.55768259	0.525524836	0.2953373556	0.986834575	-0.132801312	NA
Significance	LI1	LI2	LI3	MI1	MI2	MI3
LI1	NA					
LI2	0.3600537248	NA				
LI3	0.1607567988	0.0388874455	NA			
MI1	0.308206184	0.3664880952	0.4680308927	NA		
MI2	0.2249278395	0.3660534981	0.2460275442	0.1584436911	NA	
MI3	0.2906704802	0.3016069551	0.3849202185	0.1659431169	0.4476338637	NA

Table 1: correlations among study variables

There are both positive and negative correlations among the variables. For instance, respondents opinion on life insurance that it is a good investment option has positive relationships with both happiness and life satisfaction and responsibility but not strong. And these relationships are not significant due to the fact that the p-values are 0.36, 0.16 they are above 0.05. We fail to accept the alternative hypothesis that they in fact depend on each other. So, there are relationships but not sure whether they depend on each other i.e. we don't

know if respondents think that the life insurance is a good opportunity to indemnity as such they might not take it as a matter of happiness and responsibility. Interestingly, there is no relationship between life satisfaction and responsibility due to the fact that the correlation coefficient is negative and at the same time the relationship is significant ($0.03 < 0.05$). So there might be possibility that the respondents might not take it as responsibility just because they think that the insurance gives rise to life satisfaction and relationship is significant.

Regarding motor insurance, respondents feeling that investing in life insurance is an opportunity has negative relationships with motor insurance and these relationships are not all significant. So we might not be able to infer that the life insurance has anything to do with motor insurance. Respondents don't try to relate motor insurance with life insurance related to first variable. However, the other variables of life insurance are positively correlated with all variables of motor insurance except the last variable of life insurance with the first variable of motor insurance. In nutshell, if respondents think about life insurance as a matter of life satisfaction they don't have problem to think about motor insurance as an opportunity to invest, gives satisfaction and it is a responsibility. However, the feeling that the life insurance is a matter of responsibility belies with the feeling that motor insurance is an opportunity to invest. Of course it is true. The third level of interpretation is between the variables of motor insurance. The second variable has negative correlation with the third variable of motor insurance and the relationship is not significant. So, it seems that if respondents get satisfaction through motor insurance it doesn't necessarily imply the feeling of responsibility. However, if respondents think that motor insurance is an opportunity to invest, they tend to get the feeling of satisfaction.

Part 2: Structural equation modeling

Structural equation modeling deal with the study variables rather in parts aka first three variables of life insurance were formed as a structure and later with the rest of the variables related to motor insurance. The structure for the life insurance is as below.

Figure 1: Model proposed by study for life insurance.

Table 2: SEM parameters for life insurance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Satisfaction	1.38	0.459878683	3.0012969336	0.0029334752
LI1	-0.05	0.0777243299	-0.65868704	0.2579440196
LI2	0.06	0.075167962	0.8107969755	0.2124211263
LI3	0.03	0.0699382247	0.4853296799	0.3157535387
<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Satisfaction	1.38	0.459878683	3.0012969336	0.0029334752
LI1	-0.05	0.0777243299	-0.65868704	0.2579440196
LI2	0.06	0.075167962	0.8107969755	0.2124211263
LI3	0.03	0.0699382247	0.4853296799	0.3157535387

The above table highlights the details of parameters in the first factor structure. The parameter for satisfaction is significant and rest of the parameters are not significant. The p-value for the estimated parameter for satisfaction is 0.002 which is less than 0.05 i.e. 5 % significance level. The value for satisfaction is 1.38 while rest of the values are less than zero. So the fixed parameter is rather significantly loaded for all variables of life insurance. The following table shows the details of fit indices for factor structure one model 1 (i.e. for life insurance).

Table 3: fit indices for model 1 (factor structure for life insurance)

DF	3	DF	3
χ^2	1.6554582794	χ^2	1.6554582794
P-Value	0.6468814071	P-Value	0.6468814071
RMSEA	0	RMSEA	0
Model 1		Model 1	
AIC	13.865499353	AIC	13.865499353
BIC	6.0868220436	BIC	6.0868220436

The chi-square value is 1.644 which is not significant at 5 % significance level so the study lack sufficient evidence in support of model proposed by the researcher. The estimates (parameters) obtained through the study need not be necessarily the case in the population. The RMSEA is zero which means the error between the study estimates and standardized

estimates are insignificant. Though the sample estimates truly represents the population but the structure proposed might not hold good. The study fail to explain any latent train behind the variables under study. This further supports the null hypothesis. The following figure illustrates the model proposed for motor insurance.

Figure 2: Model proposed by study for motor insurance.

The above figure shows the model proposed by the study for motor insurance (MI stands for Motor Insurance) there are three variables for motor insurance in the data. The following are the details for study estimates (parameters)

Table 4: SEM parameters for motor insurance

Variable	Coeff.	SE	t	P-value
Satisfaction	0.87	0.0590035298	14.797882957	0.000334771
MI 1	0.07	0.0630704592	1.1807348205	0.1613976192
MI 2	0.06	0.0653997692	0.9063355309	0.2157860746
MI 3	0.05	0.3673927374	0.1469753535	0.4462364807
Variable	Coeff.	SE	t	P-value
Satisfaction	0.87	0.0590035298	14.797882957	0.000334771
MI 1	0.07	0.0630704592	1.1807348205	0.1613976192
MI 2	0.06	0.0653997692	0.9063355309	0.2157860746
MI 3	0.05	0.3673927374	0.1469753535	0.4462364807

Only the intercept i.e. fixed parameter is significant for p-value is 0.00033 which is less than 0.05 i.e. 5 % significance level. Rest of the study estimates for motor insurance are not significant. They are in agreement with null hypothesis that the model has sufficient amount of fitness. In other words the study model could explain the latent variable in the data. The following table shows the fit indices.

Table 5: fit indices for model 1 (factor structure for motor insurance)

DF	3	DF	3
K(K+1)	12	K(K+1)	12
N	30	N	30
χ^2	1.9234324147	χ^2	1.9234324147
P-Value	0.588449662	P-Value	0.588449662
RMSEA	0	RMSEA	0
Model 2		Model 2	
AIC	7.9234324147	AIC	7.9234324147
BIC	6.3547961788	BIC	6.3547961788

The chi-square measure of model fitness is not significant which means the model proposed has fitness. The variables under study are able explain a latent variable underlying the structure. Since there is second model there is some certain information regarding information criterion aka AIC and BIC. These measures might help us for inter-model comparisons. The AIC value greatly reduced from 13.85 to 7.92 which BIC remained steady, which is a positive sign regarding data explaining the structure. The following figure shows the overall study model.

Figure 3: The study model for over study.

Table 6: parameter estimates for the full model (over all study model)

Variable	Coeff.	SE	t	P-value
Satisfaction	1.93575	0.6496827245	2.9795259019	0.0028935247
loyalty1	-0.00311	0.0637417779	-0.048797062	0.480707776
loyalty2	0.01653	0.0753583302	0.2192957402	0.4139779408
loyalty3	-0.10401	0.0898618108	-1.157475012	0.128261596
Attitude 1	0.00279	0.0747379963	0.0373097247	0.4852468515
Attitude 2	-0.00017	0.0781560473	-0.002225982	0.4991195835
Attitude 3	-0.03515	0.067468634	-0.520945875	0.3031799328
Variable	Coeff.	SE	t	P-value
Satisfaction	1.93575	0.6496827245	2.9795259019	0.0028935247
loyalty1	-0.00311	0.0637417779	-0.048797062	0.480707776
loyalty2	0.01653	0.0753583302	0.2192957402	0.4139779408
loyalty3	-0.10401	0.0898618108	-1.157475012	0.128261596
Attitude 1	0.00279	0.0747379963	0.0373097247	0.4852468515
Attitude 2	-0.00017	0.0781560473	-0.002225982	0.4991195835
Attitude 3	-0.03515	0.067468634	-0.520945875	0.3031799328

There is nothing special as far as estimates are concerned. As usually the fixed parameter remained significant, which means it is not as expected by the study. Rest of the parameters are as expected. The following table shows the fit indices for the full model.

Table 7: Fit indices for the full model.

DF	3	DF	3
K(K+1)	12	K(K+1)	12
N	30	N	30
χ^2	3.7594591254	χ^2	3.7594591254
P-Value	0.2886370613	P-Value	0.2886370613
RMSEA	0.0934313397	RMSEA	0.0934313397
Model 2		Model 2	
AIC	9.7594591254	AIC	9.7594591254
BIC	8.1908228895	BIC	8.1908228895

The above table shows rather very better scenario for full model. Chi-square measure is not significant and p-value is 0.288 which is greater than 0.05 so the study is very much fit and as expected. The entire set of variables are able to measure a unique common factor underlying the data. AIC and BIC also improved when the two sub models are clubbed together. This signals that the data is very much agreement with the model proposed by the study. So the study variables though they seems to be two different sets of variables in fact trying to measure a unique variable. In other words, all the variables are trying to represents the study construct that is though life insurance is different from motor insurance they are in fact related and both of them could explain the study hypothesis that insurance might result into life satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

There are relationships but not sure whether they depend on each other i.e. we don't know if respondents think that the life insurance is a good opportunity to indemnity as such they might not take it as a matter of happiness and responsibility. There might be possibility that the respondents might not take it as responsibility just because they think that the insurance gives rise to life satisfaction and relationship is significant. We might not be able to accept that the life insurance has anything to do with motor insurance the feeling that the life insurance is a matter of responsibility belies with the feeling that motor insurance is an opportunity to invest. Of course it is true. It seems that if respondents get satisfaction through motor insurance it doesn't necessarily imply the feeling of responsibility. Though the sample estimates truly represents the population but the structure proposed might not hold good. The study fail to explain any latent train behind the variables under study. all the variables are trying to represents the study construct that is though life insurance is different from motor insurance they are in fact related and both of them could explain the study hypothesis that insurance might result into life satisfaction.

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